

A Research Review of Punjab's problem of increasing crime and its social repercussions

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Abstract

The present study investigates the dilemma of augment in crime in Punjab and its social impacts on the masses. The study is conducted to identify the reasons, its possible measures in order to mitigate its increase. The proper monitoring of all category of crime has marked out a linkage between various nexus of crime i.e. non-reporting of crimes, lack of proper detection of crimes, poor collection of evidences on the scene of occurrence, faulty investigation from the investigators side, partial trial, slow speed of trial of courts and corrupt practices prevailing in the province are main culprits of crime augmentation in the province Punjab. On the other, some social impacts, for instances, illiteracy, previous litigation, gender discrimination, unemployment, poverty, illegal arrests and detentions, political rivalries, urbanization/population explosion, excessive use of power by the political representatives, negative role of mass media and feeble criminal justice system are considered responsible for the enlargement of the premises of crimes in the province, Punjab. Implementation of correct section of law is a cause of insecurity and discomfort in the society. Moreover, the study measures the social impacts of crimes on a layman, how one's life is affected at various stages by the wrong practices of above indicators. It helps us to understand the root cause of the evils and educate the ways to mitigate the crimes in the province of Punjab. The investigation advocates us the few measures in order to mitigate the crime by practicing community policy, appropriate opportunity of education and employment, fair trials and the implementation of peace and tranquility in the society.

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Keywords: Crime & Criminology, Comparative study of crime, Historical perspective of crimes, Ratio of crimes, Social impacts of crime, causes/reasons of crime

The history of crime is as old as the history of human beings. The first crime was committed by Cain, the first son of Hazrat Adam and Eve, when he murdered his brother Abel. Inflation, low literacy rate, religious fanaticism, unemployment, poverty, previous litigations and political rivalries are major causes of insecurity and discomfort in every society. No doubt, crimes inflict enormous monetary and psychological impacts on society due to which the law and order of the society is disturbed. The criminal act gives rise to the feeling of insecurity and fear to those who have not been a victim as well in the society. Crimes can be defined as the act of an individual which is wrongful as per provided provisions of that state or province. There is no universal and permanent definition of crime exists in the world history. It differs from state to state due to difference of cultures, values and religions of the societies of the world¹.

According to the current U.S. Department of State Travel Advisory that doesn't travel to Baluchistan Province and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) Province including the former Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) of Pakistan as are vulnerable for the crimes of Dacoity and Abduction. According to the report overall 2percent increase crimes increased in Lahore in the year 2019. The road in the province of Punjab is not vigorously patrolling by police. According to US travel advisory in Lahore there is more threat to its citizen. Police response in Punjab Pakistan is between 15-25 minutes².

The Punjab Province Registered Crimes Increase Statistics are tabulated below:

Punjab Province Registered Crimes Statistics			
OFFENSES	2017	2018	2019
Murder	3914	4017	3931
Attempt to Murder	4440	5093	5446
Kidnapping/Abduction	13558	14981	15188
Dacocity	602	793	786
Robbery	9385	11128	14236
Burglary	11023	11425	12680
Cattle Theft	4721	5569	7060
Other Theft	33053	34572	50390
Others	325149	323456	380596
Total recorded Crime	405845	411034	490313

The statistic of crimes increase in Punjab are tabulated above, the different kinds of reasons are described in next chapters No.2 and 3 in detail. The application of modern techniques are given in chapter No. 4 and the pragmatic approach to mitigate the said the crimes in the province is given in the last chapter i.e. conclusion and recommendations³.

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1. Concept of Law:

The Government's mechanism of social control is called law. Law is basically passed in the parliament after pondering upon the moral, social and religious values of the people. Therefore, the local custom or local values of each region are different from the norms of other area/region and legislation is done on the basis on the social, moral and religious norms⁴.

2. Crime and Criminology:

A crime is an act or omission of human conduct harmful to others which the state is bound to prevent. It renders the deviant person liable to punishment as a result of proceedings initiated by the state organs assigned to ascertain the nature, the extent and the legal consequences of that person's wrongness.

Another definition of crime is anything made punishable by law is called crime. In Pakistan crimes are being punished under the provision of Pakistan Penal Code, 1860 which is substantive law and procedure is provided in the Code of Criminal Procedure 1898. However, special and local law has also been promulgated in a different regions or states to control crimes in the region or state. The study of crimes is Called Criminology in which society's response to crime is studied. Crime's prevention, its examination, and inheritance are also focused in criminology. Psychological impacts, modes of criminal investigation, punishments, and their efficacy are given prime importance in criminology. The rehabilitation of criminals is also studied in criminology⁵.

3. Historical perspective of crimes:

In history, crimes were mitigated by providing justice. Surety of punishments was ensured. The Holy Prophet Peace be upon Him did not differentiate among anyone in the provision of justice when the punishment was awarded to the Fatima namely women who were accused of the charges of theft. Some of the companions of the prophet peace are upon beg favor on the name of women. The Holy Prophet peace be upon him said that if the daughter of Muhammad peace be upon Him Hazrat Fatima commits the same offense she will also be awarded the same punishment. During the period of the Hazrat Umar RA the fourth caliph of Islam he said that if one dog dies on the bank of river Nile I will be inquired by on the day of resurrection. The nations die on account of failure justice and groom due to the implementation of a system of justice. It is said that crimes are mitigated by ensuring the surety of punishments not the severity of punishments. So, in history our religion imposed hard punishments for the perpetrators of saraqa, qazf, Zina, intoxication etc. The word Qisas means blood for blood. But the heirs of the vict or if, the victim is alive himself accept diyat, besides this arsh and Daman and Tazir punishments are also present. However, without the implementation of true system of punishments the crimes cannot be mitigated⁶.

4. Age of criminal responsibility in Pakistan:

In Pakistan, according to Pakistan criminal Court, 1860 the minimum age of criminal responsibility is seven years. Provisions of Section 82, Pakistan Penal Code (referred to as P.P.C. hereafter), 1860, read with Section 83 of the Code provide that a child below the age of seven years is incapable of committing an offence. The main reason behind this concept is

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that the minor is incapable of forming or possessing necessary Men's Rea for an offence whereas a child between the age of seven and twelve years can be capable of forming or possessing necessary men's rea for an offence unless it is established during the trial proceedings before the criminal courts that he has not attained maturity of understanding for the commission of a crime under study as to judge nature and consequences of his conduct to commit crimes⁷.

5. Causes of increasing crimes:

i. Crimes relations with un-Employment

The population of the province is mostly poor due to unemployment. The boys who are neglected by their families are unable to get love and attention and parental care due to which they are indulged in criminal activities. Every country whether developed or developing wishes to keep the criminal activities under strict observation with the help of law enforcement agencies in order to root out the actual causes of these illegal activities⁸. When the legal economic incentives for the people decrease, it will automatically increase the incentives of illegitimate (criminal) activities for individuals due to un-employment and deplorable economic conditions of the people⁹. The un-employed people usually engage themselves in criminal activities¹⁰.

ii. Poverty and Crimes

Poverty is a state in which a man has insufficient income to lead a sustainable life in the society. It is a collective condition of poor people or poor groups that are unable to pass a life that will enjoy the necessary amenities of life. It is true that poverty breeds crimes because every person has some basic needs of life, if needs for life are not fulfilled through legal means of life then the people try to snatch them from other people.

Food, clothes, and accommodation are the basic needs of a person that should be provided by the Govt. being constitutional responsibility. Besides white-collar crimes, it is poverty that leads the people to commit criminal activities otherwise most of the people are not by nature criminals¹¹. Due to prevailing poverty social differences among the people raises, it is the responsibility of the government to remove the reasons for poverty in society. The increasing rate of crimes should be checked and society becomes a picture of a civilized nation if, the poverty-related crimes are countered with¹².

iii. Changes in the Pattern of Life and Survival of the Fittest

Modern life has changed the definition of life now days. Due to modern machinery and new inventions in the field of new machines the demand of physical labor is decreasing day by day. As the machines output as compared with the human output is more. The people prefer to use the machines in order to meet the demands of the simmering population. This injustice can be extinguished by the proper policy of the government by the effective regulations of the law enforcement agencies¹³.

iv. Homeless people and Crimes

Most of the people in the big cities are homeless. Homeless people become easy prey to involve them in criminal activities, especially in human trafficking crimes. Due to poverty money lending on interest business is common in the province. The poor people make money on interest to fulfill their material needs of life and when they often failed to pay back the

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same to the wealthy class then they are subjected to forced labor. When the homeless poor people try to run away from that place then they have to the music of criminal charges against them. Secondly, homeless people have the least identification, they usually commit offenses in one area, and thereafter, they move to other areas in order to conceal their identity from the police departments detectives¹⁴.

v. *Education links with crimes increase*

Education and crimes go hand in hand. Education is inversely related to crime. It is said that education is a panacea for all sorts of crimes. The countries where education and literacy rate are high their crime rate is low. The reason behind this is very simple. Education increases consciousness among the masses due to which they respect the national and international laws. On the other hand, education produces skilled labor. The skilled labor needs not to indulge in property-related crimes. So, if we want to really decrease the crime rate then we need to increase the literacy rate of the country.

vi. *Health facilities and crimes*

The countries with better economic opportunities provide more efficient health facilities to their populace. The present government of Punjab Pakistan is providing health opportunities to the people by issuing health cards to them. Healthy people are more useful for the country's interest. Healthy people are able to earn more economic opportunities due to which the crimes rate decreases in the country¹⁵.

vii. *Economic Development and Crimes*

Countries that have strong economy manage better systems for controlling crimes. Economic opportunities provide infrastructure for parental care and education facilities due to which crimes are mitigated. Due to economic opportunities the countries are able to achieve best law enforcement agencies to prevent, counter and combat crimes. When the people are not hungry and their demands are fulfilled by the state, they need to indulge themselves in different kinds of crimes. Best economic opportunities end unemployment and reduce poverty among the populace. In the countries where the economy is strong there the legislative body is also strong along with institutions that help the country to fight with the crimes¹⁶.

viii. *Previous Litigations*

Previous litigation also has promoted the rate of crimes in the province. The people did not leave their age-old enmity on the pretext of their so-called honor. They did not think about the offspring's future but their family traditions are more important for them and resultantly their whole family collapsed in spite of this they remain adamant to their point¹⁷.

ix. *Gender Discrimination*

Gender discrimination is also the main reason for crime increase in the district. Male is considered as earning hands and female are dependent on men on account of financial matters. Even on similar labor, males are paid more labor emoluments than women. Women are considered in our society to procure offspring and to perform domestic obligations only. Women are not even provided fundamental rights of proper nourishment and honor. She does all the necessary service in order to keep happy her family but she is failed to get respect and honor in return of her services for the family and equal status comparative to men. The homeless women mostly indulge in the practice of prostitution and themselves use to live in the brothel houses¹⁸.

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x. *False Lodging of Criminal Cases (Illegal arrests and detentions)*

False registration of criminal cases is also very common in the police department on the orders of the political elite, landlords, pressure groups of the lawyer's community, and concerning with the press community. It is seen in some of the cases people in order to take their personal revenge use the local police as a weapon and bribes them for the registration of false cases even against the innocent people that are booked in the guilt or wrongs which they even did not know. They are convicted due to the bad performance of the weak criminal justice system of the province.

6. Powers of Police Department regarding Arrests and Detentions:

There are two kinds of powers of Police regarding arrest and detention under Schedule-II of the Pakistan Penal Code. They are authorized to arrest without a warrant any person against whom there is "reasonable apprehension" of being involved or "concerned in the commission of the cognizable offense. In the second category, the police department cannot arrest without the prior permission of the magistrate regarding the arrest of the offender in non-cognizable cases. In addition to the above said the police can also arrest a person about whom there is information that the accused is concerned with the cognizable offense¹⁹.

i. *Arrested Criminals be produced before the Illaqa Magistrate:*

In order to provide protection from arbitrary arrest and detention by the police department and to check the unfettered powers of police personnel and to protect the citizens from the bogus custody, the police authorities are duty-bound to present the accused person after arrest before the Illaqa magistrate within 24 hours when the police arrest without a warrant. The illaqa magistrate if, considers that the custody of the accused person should be given to the police then he can order for the provision of remand and if, if the magistrate that there is no need to provide the custody of the accused person to the police authorities then he has the power to send him to judicial custody. If, when the accused person is produced before the illaqa magistrate and the illaqa magistrate is satisfied that the accused person is innocent and maliciously involved him by the police authorities then he can discharge the accused person²⁰.

7. Political Victimization:

According to the respondents, some of the legislators of Pakistan are involved in supporting the criminals. They manage to appoint a station house officer of their own choice and they invest in this regard. After the appointment of police officers their own choice they try to take advantage of registration of cases and investigation of their own choice. Those people who intend to take justice from the police department firstly have to visit the Deras of the political elite otherwise the concerned police officer did not listen to him properly. The police officers who are involved in corrupt practice should be removed from the department permanently in order to clean the mess²¹.

8. Multiple Approaches for the elimination of Crimes:

i. *Record of CRO*

The Criminal Record Office in the law enforcement agencies has revolutionized to find out desperate/hardened criminals by utilizing their previous data and modern scientific

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evidence. A number of criminal occurrences have been traced out in the province due to good efforts of this office. When the criminals allege before the Hon'ble courts that they are respectable citizens of the district then their criminal record (History Sheet) is produced before the Hon'ble courts with the help of this department that they are previous record holder. This department helps to point out the criminal history of the culprits and to collect the data of the criminals for future usage²².

ii. *Mobile data (CDR)*

Mobile phone call data of the complainant and respondents are obtained which helps to locate the criminals by using the techniques of tower locations and calls contacts within the time of occurrence. The mobile CDR of the parties is obtained and their comparison helps them in locating the actual criminals of the occurrence. The mobile CDR further helps to check the veracity of the evidence whether the criminal was present at the site of occurrence or otherwise. The technique of mobile CDR is also useful as many unknown criminals have been arrested and sent to judicial lock-up due to the thanks of this technique. The Gangs have been busted by utilizing the mobile CDR technique. It is an important tool of modern evidence and locating the evidence identity and admissible in courts of law²³.

iii. *Photography of place of occurrence*

Photography of place of occurrence must be ensured at the earliest otherwise it can be tempered, or destroyed by public, rain, smoke, dust, hurricane, and other atmospheric conditions. No doubt the best camera is the human eye so, the first responder must keep eyes open and see the available evidence and grasp it absolutely. If you have photos of wounds then Doctor may take assistance from it in writing MLCs and no one be able to exploit the evidence. Photography helps to understand the Gang due to their pattern and by collection of evidence everyone be able to understand Psychology and Behavior of the criminals and the causes of their criminal behaviors. It helped to properly furnish the evidence before the courts of law through the prosecution department²⁴.

iv. *Crime Mapping*

The technique is used by analysts of law enforcement agencies to measure, examine and study crime occurrence patterns in the province. The basic function of this technique is to identify and determine the crime's hot spot in the province due to which they will be able themselves to know the main reasons behind the occurrence of the crime and to know what are the main causes of the particular crimes occurring in the society. The crime mapping technique helps law enforcement agencies to review their policies to counter and curb the crime rate in the province²⁵.

v. *Geo Tagging*

The information received through Geo Tagging includes place coordinates (latitude and longitude), distance and place names. Basically, geo-tagging gives location-based information about the individuals. It helps to locate the position of the criminals with the help of a mobile tower and mobile IMEI number. Geo-tagging may occur when a photograph or video footage is made, the images are posted online. The cell phones with built-in GPS facilities are capable of geo-tagging photograph that helps in determining the position of the criminals. So, by utilizing this technique enough information may be collected to arrest the offenders of unknown identity.

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vi. *Security of vulnerable establishment*

The security of vulnerable establishments and main points of the province is highly important to manage the law-and-order conditions of the country. The law enforcement agencies have done a security audit of the important points about that security threats have been received. The main focus is on pumps, CNG stations, BTS mobile cellular towers, Churches, banks and important buildings, etc to avoid law and order situations and ensure full-proof security of the important points. The vulnerable establishments are notified under the provisions of The Punjab Vulnerable Establishment Act-2015 by the Deputy Commissioner. The advisory committee is constituted who issue them advice and warning slips to fulfill the gap mentioned in the security audit and point out their discrepancies in order to avoid any untoward situation²⁶.

vii. *Front desk at Police Station*

The establishment of the front desk at police stations in the province of Punjab is a good initiative for serving the public and in order to mitigate their suffering at the grass root level. The online data is always proved useful and it gives useful information when needed. Front Desk is a reception office in the police stations that provides a good responsive and pleasant environment to the public to redress their complaints²⁷.

9. Recommendations:

In order to ensure justice and mitigate the crimes rate in Punjab Province following recommendations must be strictly adhered to, for ensuring the desired results:

i. *Maintenance of Public Order*

Peace Committees in the province will be reconstituted and activated. The close liaison will be kept with the Mohallah/Village Committees, notables/ respectable and elected representatives of the public, and they will be associated in resolving the conflicts prevailing in the society. Collection, analysis, and sharing of information with other sister intelligence agencies on political and religious issues should be ensured in letter a spirit. Close liaison with religious, labor, student leaders, the business community, and advocates can help in mitigating the crime rate in the province. Coordination at all levels at Mohallah/ Village Committees, notables, elected representatives, citizens, elective representatives, community police councils should be ensured. Anti-riot capability in police stations and police lines as well as at the sub-divisional level should be strengthened.

ii. *Community Policing*

For success and to achieve the required goals following steps should be taken for mitigation of crimes rate through community policing in the areas of jurisdiction:

a. Daily interaction with Community in order to collect information

b. Committees to be formed at District/Police Station level in which Retired Army/ Police/ Judges / Bureaucrats and well reputed personalities should be the members of the committees which solve the matters of the populace on priority basis in order to mitigate the suffering of the people.

c. Stakeholder Management can reduce the crimes in the society.

d. Market Committees formulation in the cities resolve the matter of the concerned business people in their areas of jurisdiction.

e. Students, Internships and volunteers help about reporting of crimes can help in

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arresting the crimes in the locality.

f. ThikriPehra can play role to stop crimes against property and persons²⁸.

iii. Welfare of the Force

Welfare of the force should be ensured by adopting following ways:

a. Insurance of the police employees should be ensured that in case death during service although the incumbent government has done a lot in this field for the welfare of the police officers and employees.

b. Shuttle Service for the police service for arrival and departure.

c. Messes Renovations is highly needed. Improvement of Barracks and with air coolers and Darbars.

d. Sports/Entertainment Activities should be arranged for them

Conclusion:

This article is to detect the dilemma of augment of crimes and its social impacts on general public in the province. The social factors are temperature changes, previous disputes, political rivalries, un-employment, poverty, gender discrimination, non-provision of a fair trial to the population, population explosion, rampant corrupt practices prevailing in the societies, weak criminal justice system and negative impacts of media including social media upon the society is promoting crimes rate in the society. It has been concluded media's vested interest causes negative journalism which hinders the process of fair criminal investigation in Punjab due to which the crime rate in the province is increasing. The presences of some pressure groups that cause harassment to the criminal investigator also hinder to conduct of fair criminal investigation and further fair trial resultantly the crimes in the province are augmenting.

The laborious work plan, meager salaries, un-healthy atmosphere, no fixed duty hours, pressurized job, harassment at all level criminal investigators and no proper refresher courses for the detective/ investigators, no enhancement of capabilities of the contingents, the mere issuance of show cause notice on minor issues and exemplary punishment, poor condition of the vehicle of the police department, budgetary issues for the lower tiers, non-provision of proper investigation cost to the investigator, non-provision of traveling expenditures to rank and file, no job securities to the investigation officers, due to un-fixed duty hours and hardships in getting leave for the employee of the department cause family issues for them. Their family life remains in a doldrums state.

The investigation officers are not provided with the modern facilities for the collection of evidence due to which effective investigation is not possible. There is a lack of trust among officers and officials of the department is hurdling the performance of the department. In the department, no research-based study to counter and mitigate rates in the province is present in letter and spirit. The department should recruit psychologists and criminologists to study why specific crimes happen in specific areas. How the specific crimes can be mitigated.

The salaries to the employees of the security employees should be provided in comparison with their workload but in our case is different here usually officers/ official who sits in air conditioner rooms enjoy hefty salaries even duty hours are also less and not hardened.

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